

PATTERN RECOGNITION USING COMPUTER VISION

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Abstract

This project, “Pattern Recognition using Computer Vision” focuses on developing a system capable of identifying and interpreting patterns in visual data through the use of machine learning algorithms. The goal is to address the limitations of traditional pattern recognition systems, such as low accuracy and inefficiency, by leveraging Logistic Regression. The proposed system will be evaluated on various datasets, with potential applications in fields such as healthcare, security, and autonomous vehicles. Pattern recognition is a fundamental aspect of computer vision, enabling machines to interpret and understand visual data by identifying patterns, objects, or features within images. With the advent of deep learning the field has seen significant advancements, leading to more accurate and efficient systems. This project focuses on leveraging these advancements to develop a comprehensive pattern recognition system that can be applied in various real-world scenarios, including image classification, object detection.

Keywords— Computer Vision, Feature Extraction, Logistic Regression, Model Accuracy, Pattern Recognition.

1. INTRODUCTION

The growing demand for intelligent systems capable of understanding and interpreting human activities has led to significant advancements in the fields of pattern recognition and computer vision. This research focuses on leveraging Logistic Regression (LR) in pattern recognition to develop an efficient, interpretable, and scalable model for human activity recognition. By classifying visual data from images, our approach identifies and categorizes human activities based on their unique patterns and features, either through raw pixel values or extracted visual cues. Human Activity Recognition (HAR) is challenging yet crucial for applications across healthcare, surveillance, and human-device interaction. Existing methodologies often rely on neural networks, which, while effective, can be complex and resource-intensive. In contrast, this research proposes a Logistic Regression Perception Network aimed at simplifying activity recognition tasks while maintaining accuracy. Our model aims to predict human actions by utilizing statistical approaches and historical data for informed pattern recognition. Through this approach, we contribute to the development of a lightweight, real-time solution for human activity classification that can be effectively applied in various fields where rapid and reliable activity recognition is essential. Logistic Regression (LR) is one of the most fundamental and widely used algorithms in the field of machine learning and pattern recognition. Despite its name, it is primarily used for classification tasks rather than regression, making it a powerful tool for binary classification and, with extensions, for multi-class classification problems. In the context of computer vision, where the objective is often to

classify or recognize patterns within images, Logistic Regression plays a key role in simplifying complex tasks into manageable problems. Pattern recognition involves identifying patterns, structures, or regularities in data, and one of the most common applications of this field is image classification, where the goal is to label images based on their content (such as identifying objects, faces, or digits). Computer vision, a subset of artificial intelligence (AI), deals with enabling machines to interpret and make decisions based on visual data, typically in the form of images or videos. Logistic Regression serves as a foundational technique in such tasks, providing a simple yet effective approach to image classification problems.

Figure 1 System Architecture

User Input

- The user provides input using a live camera (like a webcam).
- This live camera captures the real-time image or video.

Pre-trained System

On the system side, there's a trained dataset already prepared. It goes through the following steps:

Pre-processing

- This step cleans and prepares the data/images from the dataset so that they're ready to be used for training and comparison.

Feature Extraction

- The system looks at the input (live image) and extracts important features (like shapes, patterns, etc.).
- It also detects specific parameters from the image for testing.

Logistic Regression Algorithm (LR Algorithm)

- The system uses a machine learning algorithm (Logistic Regression in this case).
- It compares the extracted features from the live input image with the features from the pre-trained dataset.

Output Detection

- After comparison, the system detects the human activity (e.g., sitting, walking, waving, etc.).
- The result is displayed back to the user.

Problem Statement

- Recently to detect and identify human Activity is so difficult. So, we are going to implement a proposed model for a Logistic Regression (LR) Perception Network on image processing.
- Traditional methods struggle with accuracy and real-time performance.
- Need for a system that is fast, efficient, and applicable in multiple domains

2. METHODOLOGY

Data Preprocessing

- Collecting images/videos from datasets or real-time camera feed.
- Applying image enhancement techniques (grayscale conversion, noise reduction).

Pose Estimation Model

- Using Open Pose, Pose Net, or Media Pipe to extract body key points.
- Converting detected key points into numerical vectors for further processing.

Feature Engineering

- Extracting key features such as joint angles, movement speed, and relative position.
- Normalizing and structuring data for classification

Machine Learning Model

- Applying Logistic Regression to classify movements.
- Training the model using labeled dataset (standing, sitting, punching, kicking, etc.).
- Evaluating accuracy using Confusion Matrix & Precision-Recall Analysis.

Real-Time Implementation

- Deploying the trained model for real-time activity detection.
- Displaying results via GUI (Tkinter) or Web Interface.

3. RESULTS

Home Page

Figure 2 Home Page

Registration Page

Figure 3 Registration Page

Login Page

Figure 4 Login Page

Live Activity Detection

Figure 5 Live Activity Detection

Figure 6 Sitting Analysis

Figure 7 Live Activity Detection

Applications

Smart Homes

- Adjusting devices based on user posture (e.g., sitting vs. standing)

Healthcare & Elderly Care:

- Detecting falls, posture correction, physiotherapy monitoring

Fitness & Sports:

- Workout tracking, real-time feedback on movements.

Security & Surveillance:

- Detecting fights, suspicious activities in public places.

Virtual Reality (VR) & Gaming:

- Gesture-based controls, immersive gaming experience

4. CONCLUSION

All The project successfully demonstrates the potential of machine learning and computer vision in revolutionizing pattern recognition systems. By overcoming the limitations of traditional methods, the developed model offers enhanced accuracy, efficiency, and versatility. The project not only contributes to the academic understanding of computer vision but also opens avenues for practical applications in various industries. Regression can serve as an effective method for simpler, real-time pattern

recognition applications, particularly when the goal is to quickly deploy a lightweight, interpretable solution with reasonable accuracy.

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